

ENHANCING THE METHOD OF IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF CAR DRIVER TRAINING IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Annotation The number of cars is increasing in the roads due to an increase in the number of interested in the management of the vehicle in our country. This article is relevant in quality supporting drivers.

This article calls on the history of traffic rules and techniques and techniques in the country.

Keywords: Car Driver, Training Methods, Road Rules, Cloudy System, Mobile Application, Game Technology

Introduction. The number of cars is increasing in the roads due to an increase in the number of interested in the management of the vehicle in our country. In this case, the drivers will take a car management exam once during the receipt of the driver's license and will have a positive assessment. The Single Exam Center officer is a simple method, that is, he is considered to take the exam, if he takes the test questions correctly and controlled. Drivers and vehicles on the roads mean that the demand for self-suffrage is to ensure itself.

- **Analysis of literature review.** The order of movement on the roads was the need to determine the registration of the law.

It is known from history that the first shovel-type semaphore device that regulates traffic was built by engineer Dj. Knight built it in 1868 next to the English Parliament building in London. It's complete with buildable and green light filters and state-of-the-art equipment.

The emergence of self-propelled light carriages in the 18th century required the development of rules for their movement. In 1879, Frenchman Nicolas-Joseph

Cunot was the inventor of the first steam car. The car with a gasoline engine - the prototype of the modern car - was created in 1885-1886 by German engineers Karl Benz and Gottlieb Daimler. It was they who were officially recognized as the inventors of the automobile, although the names of many other inventors who created all kinds of easy-to-drive structures are mentioned in history.

The rules of action for cars were first introduced in France on August 14, 1893. Road signs and traffic lights were used to relieve movement. The first four railway crosses and rail curves - hazardous roads, characters such as risk as an unevenness uneven removes were approved in Paris in Paris in 1909. These rounds of symptoms are almost fully consistent with the signal and symbols used in current symptoms and are also determined today.

The road signs and road lines were used. Their use was regulated to rectify the growing cars. In 1926, the international system of road signs was replenished with two more characters: "Non-protected railroad intersections" and "it is forced to stop." In the Soviet Union, the first road signal sign technical specifications were developed and implemented this year.

In 1931, the Convention on the Road signal was adopted at the Republic of Roadeva in Geneva. The number of characters increased to 26, which divided into three groups: warning, commanding, and indicator.

Until the Second World War, there were two main systems of road signs in different countries around the world. In terms of the 1931 Convention in the European system, mainly the symbols were used. The English-American system has used inscriptions instead of characters.

Until 1940, our country had no source of rule, the development and approval of the local government belonged to the authority of the Organization. In 1940, the Rules of the first standard movement were confirmed, on which it has developed less or multi-one rules.

During the Second World War the united system of road signals worldwide began. In 1949 he decided on the traffic convention and road signs and signals on

the international road conference in Geneva. He was added to the Soviet Union in 1959.

The streets and roads where the unique city and settlements of urban areas and settlements were first in the first country were first added in 1961. Then after the slight processing, these rules were re-confirmed in 1965.

In the road sector, the next round of international development legislative development was adopted in 1968, adopted in 1968, and the convention on road conversion and road signals, signals. These conventions were later processed in the European Agenda in 1971, as well as a convention in accordance with European conditions. The Soviet Union has ratified (approved) these documents and practically implemented the rules in the organization of the country's road movement. Traffic rules of traffic based on the 1968 Convention and the 1971 European Agreement Additional were created.

In 1949, the decision on road signs, signals on signals in Geneva was practiced in our country until January 1, 1973, that is, until GOST 10807 - 71.

From June 1, 1980, a new version of the rules was included. The editorial number of 1980 was different from the previous rules with fully processed departments and road signs. The next amendments in the rules came into force on January 1, 1987.

Currently, traffic rules in almost all countries are based on traffic convention on road traffic, road signs and signs. I am similar to this side. But in some other countries, including the UK, Japan, India and other countries, there is a little difference in the order that everyone accepts the movement. In these countries there are differences in the road system and the left-sided action is installed.

Even during the time of independent Uzbekistan, working on traffic rules has not stopped. The first principle of independent Uzbekistan was reached its efforts in 1994.

The rules of traffic in currently force were introduced in 2001 and the second edition of changes and additions has been developed in 2010.

Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 370 of December 24, 2015, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 12-2 Resolution No. 172 of April was adopted and attachments were made to road provisions.

PQ-3127 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-3127 of July 11, 2018 Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 408 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan and to further improve the procedure for the provision of non-governmental vehicle drivers, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on February 23, 2018 139- Decisions on the System "Preparation of Automotans Drives, Retraining and Advanced Training" [3]

In the connection of practice with Mazomo theory. Scientific knowledge should also appear based on the needs of manufacturing on the basis of the needs of manufacturing and serve that knowledge, and to acquire this knowledge in practice, and to use it in practice.

- **Research Methodology.** Game Technology has proved the high efficiency of all ages from games to young people, especially in teaching traffic rules for young children, using competitions. The value of the game cannot be finished with fun and rest opportunities. It is his phenomenon, entertainment, he can learn, creativity, and an example. The elementary school age is distinguished by the brightness and speed of perception, with the ease of access to images. Children are easily involved in any activity, especially the game, form themselves in the group game, forms playing with objects. [6]

Game Technologies in Teaching Traffic Rules:

- - mobile, sports, exercise;
- - logical tasks, games - riddles;
- - playing role;
- - road miniature theater, games - dramatization;
- - Intelligent and training games, travel, quizzes;
- - Didactic;

- - Published on the desktop, with objects.
- Therefore, it is necessary to pay attention to the norms of the student in teaching the rules of traffic, the learned material should be paid to the emotional imprint in his memory. Technology is a chain of actions and operations aimed at results. The main goal of pedagogical technology is to increase the efficiency of the educational process, to ensure that students achieve planned results of students. In institutions providing driving services, they follow legislation and manuals in the organization of the educational process.
- The main form of education is full-time. However, if driving school has the technical ability to form webinars, remote teaching is only allowed during the study of theoretical part.
- Some driving schools have a car simulators, which allows the car's movement fully. A computer screen is used instead of the front window. Despite such simulators allow them to take true driving skills, classes are held within the framework of the theoretical training course.

The use of information computer technology in familiarization to the rules of traffic will provide the lesson unconventional, meaningful, various techniques and methods of teaching. Animation, slide presentations, films will allow people to actively cognitive to the learned events. The material support methods will help to concentrate attention to long-term focus, and at the same time, this will help strengthen the new knowledge taken at the same time . I think the use of cars used in the Korea is very effective because cars are made automatically to break the rules.

-Analysis and results. About 75 percent of accidents in road transport occurs due to the violation of the traffic rules of drivers. The most dangerous types of offenses still remain driving the speed, ignoring road signs, traveling to opposite transport. Often bad ways (mostly slippery), malfunctions - first - brake, second - wheels and tires) leads to accidents.

By the above, the above information is that about 75% of all road transport accidents occur due to the drivers of traffic rules. In addition, a third of road accidents is the result of the evil teaching drivers. They are not eligible to manage the appropriate category of vehicle or have purchased driving licenses altogether. At the meeting, the corrupt case in the field was critical on the basis of state statistical data. Analyzes show that accidents:

- 45 percent of drivers disregarding rules;
- Investigators of drivers 10 percent;
- 25% of road condition and infrastructure are not meet required;
- There is a result of 20 percent of the rules of pedestrians that they do not follow the rules.

Figure 1. Analysis of accidents.

All of the above problems are directly related to both social and economic and security issues. Therefore, in 2022, we implement the National Program "Safe Road and Safe" in all regions, "the President said.

For example, 46 percent of 7.7 million offenses detected in 2021 are aggravated. Especially:

- Interpretation management Samarkand (12,000), Tashkent region (8.5 thousand) and Fergana region (7.5 thousand) and in Tashkent (7,000);
- Go to the red lamp is Tashkent region (62,000), Samarkand (51,000) and in Tashkent, in Tashkent (47 thousand).

In addition, adding more extra time to a severe road transport accident, as a result of a long time.

The most dangerous types of violation of rough rule:

- 1. Exceeding speed limits;*
- 2. Going to the opposite row;*
- 3. Drunk driving.*

The rough rule prevents the analysis of 2020-2021, as a result of analysis decreased by 12%, the strengthening of cameras and control in the road.

Figure 2. Their rule between 2020-2021 violates violations

Figure 3th of the drivers who have committed.

In the 2021 drivers under the age of 25, 2021, drivers under the age of 25, and 2,077 drivers under the age of 30. These figures are shown that drivers do not assess the situation in knowledge skills and the right situations correctly.

- Conclusion/Recommendations. In order to remotely support students' learning level, one of the most widely used by "IOS" systems "IOS" is Android, is Android, for phones running on this Android system, "Fundamentals of traffic rules and traffic safety". The mobile application was developed on the subject. The colates of students and driving students in the colonic system and other methods were raised in percent of the following percentages:

General functions of drivers (14.2 percent), the liabilities of the driver when the traffic accident (20.2%), pedestrians (16.2 percent), liabilities of passengers (8.2 percent), traffic lights (16.2 percent), traffic lights. and regulators (23.2 percent), warning and accident (21.2 percent), movement, maneuvization (28.2 percent), position of vehicles (11, 2 percent), movement speed (9.2 percent), Passing (8.2 percent), stop and parking (14.2 percent), movement at intersection (26.2 percent), Pedestrians Traffic of toothpaces and vehicles (36.2%), railways (16.2 percent), movement on highways (7.2 percent), movement in residential areas (17.2 percent) Intaching vertices in upright and slope (8.2 percent), benefits of directional vehicles (9.2%), use of external lighting devices Dationing (11.2 percent), teaching mechanical vehicles (11.2 percent), transportation of vehicles (17.2 percent), human transportation (17.2 percent), freight (19.2%) , purchase of bicycles, moped and carts of carts, as well as the expulsion of animals (21.2 percent), to regulate the traffic safety, the number and recognition of vehicles. Signs sets (8.6 percent), road signs (15.8 percent), traffic lines (10 percent), an increase in traffic levels, the test river.

Collarities of the mobile application here:

- The lack of internet is not needed, which also allows you to read in areas with no extra costs (free distribution of aircraft to students) and Internet operation.
- The mobile application programs as a presentation, not in the form of the book, which is convenient in the student's reading process.

- The placement of a video lecture at the end of the presentation creates the convenience of students and listeners.

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